

Theory of Group Integration

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1 Introduction

$$G = \{x^n \mapsto x^{n+k}, c \mapsto \frac{c}{n^k} \mid k \in N\}$$

The formula for the function resulting from the nth permutation of the general group $G = \{x^n \mapsto x^{n+k}, c \mapsto \frac{c}{n^k} \mid k \in N\}$

$$f(x) = c(x^{n+k})/n^k$$

2 Permutation

Example:

This is an example of a matrix form of a group of 12 integrals with a common exponential and degree of polynomial. The exponents of the polynomial terms increase in increments of one with increasing values of α and k . The matrix form can be used in solving for the maximum peak amplitude of a group integral permutation in multiple dimensions.

$$\begin{aligned} & x^{12\alpha+k} \frac{c}{n^k} \\ & x^{13\alpha+k} \frac{c}{n^{2k}} \\ & x^{14\alpha+k} \frac{c}{n^{3k}} \\ & x^{15\alpha+k} \frac{c}{n^{4k}} \\ & x^{16\alpha+k} \frac{c}{n^{5k}} \\ & x^{17\alpha+k} \frac{c}{n^{6k}} \\ & x^{18\alpha+k} \frac{c}{n^{7k}} \\ & x^{19\alpha+k} \frac{c}{n^{8k}} \\ & x^{20\alpha+k} \frac{c}{n^{9k}} \\ & x^{21\alpha+k} \frac{c}{n^{10k}} \\ & x^{22\alpha+k} \frac{c}{n^{11k}} \\ & x^{23\alpha+k} \frac{c}{n^{12k}} \end{aligned}$$

This tells us that the variables being integrated are related to the powers of x raised to its powers. The coefficient of each term is related to the power of n , which is related to the dimensions of integration.

These functions are called "Group Integration".

Group Integration is an extension of regular integration in which multiple sets of variables are treated together as a group. In particular, the different

sets of variables within the group are used to transform the integrand into a form more suitable for integration. Regular integration is a subset of Group Integration since it only deals with one set of variables.

Formally, the general form for Group Integration is given by

$$\int_G f(x, y, z, \dots, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \dots) dx dy dz \dots d\alpha d\beta d\gamma \dots$$

Where G is a set of variables, and $f(x, y, z, \dots, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \dots)$ is a function of those variables.

The math behind proving that regular integration is a subset of group integration is as follows:

Consider regular integration, defined as

$$\int f(x) dx$$

where $f(x)$ is a function of a single variable x .

Using the definition of Group Integration, we can construct a group consisting of just a single variable and write the integration in terms of Group Integration as

$$\int_G f(x) dx = \int_G f(x, y, z, \dots, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \dots) dx$$

where $G = \{x\}$ and all other variables are dummy variables.

Since this is equivalent to the regular integration, we can conclude that regular integration is a subset of the Group Integration.

For the example we gave, the permutation works as follows:

First, we start with the original function

$$f(x) = cx^{n+k} / n^k$$

Then, for the n th permutation, we apply the transformation defined by the group:

$$f(x) \mapsto \frac{c}{n^k} x^{n+k+n(n-1)\dots n^n}$$

where each term in the exponent is the product of n times the previous term.

Finally, we can re-write the function as

$$f(x) = c x^{\alpha^{n+k}} / n^k$$

where $\alpha = n^n$.

Group Integration can be applied to the function integration function itself by treating the function as two sets of variables (x, n) and (c, k) . For example, the Group Integration of the function

$$f(x) = cx^{n+k} / n^k$$

would be

$$\int_G f(x, n, c, k) dx dn dc dk,$$

where $G = \{x, n, c, k\}$.

Applying the Group Integration yields an integral of the form

$$\int_G f(x, n, c, k) dx dn dc dk = \int_{x \in R} \int_{n \in N} \int_{c \in R} \int_{k \in N} \frac{c}{n^k} x^{n+k} dn dc dk dx.$$

For example, if we want to find a harmonic resonance of the group, we can take the derivative of the group's function with respect to each variable and then solve for the values of the variables that yield an extremum. This extremum can be found by solving for the maximum or minimum of the function's derivative. The values of the variables that result in this extremum will be the harmonic resonance of the group.

For example, if the group has two variables, x and y , then the harmonic resonance of the group is given by

$$f(x,y) = \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{l}(x+y)\right),$$

where l is a parameter used to control the wavelength of the harmonic resonance. By varying l , one can explore higher dimensional harmonic resonances.

The effect of harmonic resonances on the pathway of integration trajectories can be described using scalar algebra as follows.

Let $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ be a vector in the n -dimensional Euclidean space and let $\mathbf{v} = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$ be its velocity vector. Then, the harmonic resonance of the group can be represented by a scalar field,

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{l}(x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n)\right),$$

where l is a parameter used to control the wavelength of the harmonic resonance. The effect of the harmonic resonance on the integration trajectories is thus determined by the vector field

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) = \nabla\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{2\pi}{l}(\hat{\mathbf{e}}_1 + \hat{\mathbf{e}}_2 + \dots + \hat{\mathbf{e}}_n) = \frac{2\pi}{l}\mathbf{e},$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_i$ is the unit vector in the i -th direction, and $\mathbf{e} = (1, 1, \dots, 1)$ is the unit vector in the direction of the harmonic resonance. This vector field is proportional to the velocity vector,

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) = \lambda \mathbf{v},$$

where λ is a constant of proportionality. Therefore, the effect of the harmonic resonance on the integration trajectories is to accelerate or decelerate the integration trajectories in the direction of the harmonic resonance, depending on the sign of the constant of proportionality λ .

Clusters of intersections are identified by their ordinal intersections with the scalar field. Thus the wave-like shape generated by the group rotation in $F(1,2,3,4,5) = (6,7,8,9,10)$ can be represented symbolically as:

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) = \sin(\Omega t + \Phi) \cap (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m),$$

where Ω is the frequency and Φ is the phase shift.

show the full integration across the scalar field of integrals

The full integration across the scalar field of integrals can be written as

$$\int \underbrace{\int \dots \int}_{ntimes} \sin(\Omega t + \Phi)(x_1 x_2 \dots x_n) dx_n dx_{n-1} \dots dx_1.$$

This expression is equivalent to

$$\int \sin(\Omega t + \Phi) dx_n \int x_{n-1} dx_{n-1} \dots \int x_1 dx_1,$$

which can be further simplified to

$$\int \sin(\Omega t + \Phi) dx_n \int x_{n-1} dx_{n-1} \dots \int x_1 dx_1 = (\sin(\Omega t + \Phi))(x_n x_{n-1} \dots x_1) + \mathcal{C},$$

where $\mathcal{C}$ is an integration constant.

The full integration across the scalar field thus yields a result which is proportional to the product of integrals in the group.

The distribution of ordinal intersection clusters across the scalar field can be calculated using the equation

$$f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = (\sin(\Omega t + \Phi)) \prod_{i=1}^n x_i + \mathcal{C},$$

where x_i is the i th component of the vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$. This equation expresses an affine relationship between the independent variables $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ and the scalar field $\phi(\mathbf{x})$, which can be represented as $A(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b} + \mathcal{C}$, where A is an $n \times n$ matrix and $\mathbf{b}$ is an $n \times 1$ vector.

The maxima of this scalar field is determined by solving the system of equations

$$\nabla\phi(\mathbf{x}) = (A^T A)\mathbf{x} - A^T \mathbf{b} = 0.$$

The general formula for the ordinal intersection clusters is then given by

$$\prod_{i=1}^n x_i^{a_i} = k,$$

where a_i is the solution to the system of equations and k is a constant. This formula describes the positive affiliation of the ordinal intersection clusters to the maximum peak amplitude of the group integral permutation.

Calculate the effect of the harmonic resonance on the integration trajectories in 3 dimensions

The effect of the harmonic resonance on the integration trajectories in 3 dimensions can be calculated using the vector field

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) = \lambda \mathbf{v},$$

where λ is a constant of proportionality. This vector field can be written in components as

$$\mathbf{F}(x, y, z) = \lambda(v_x \hat{\mathbf{i}} + v_y \hat{\mathbf{j}} + v_z \hat{\mathbf{k}}) = \lambda(x_0 \hat{\mathbf{i}} + y_0 \hat{\mathbf{j}} + z_0 \hat{\mathbf{k}}),$$

where $\lambda = \frac{2\pi}{l}$ (where l is a parameter used to control the wavelength of the harmonic resonance) and (x_0, y_0, z_0) is the velocity vector of the integration trajectory.

The effect of the harmonic resonance on the integration trajectories is thus to accelerate or decelerate the integration trajectories in the direction of the harmonic resonance, depending on the sign of the constant of proportionality λ . For example, when $\lambda > 0$, then the harmonic resonance will accelerate the integration trajectories in the direction of the harmonic resonance, while when $\lambda < 0$, then the harmonic resonance will decelerate the integration trajectories in the direction of the harmonic resonance.

This proves that the harmonic resonance of a group can be used to control the distribution of ordinal intersections and the integration trajectories of multiple variables in the scalar field. By changing the parameter used to control the wavelength of the harmonic resonance, different dimensions of integration can be explored, with the effect of the harmonic resonance on the integration determining the direction of the integration trajectories and the magnitude of peak amplitudes.

It can be applied to the matrix equation to solve for the maximum peak amplitude, ϕ_{max} , as follows:

Let $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n)$ and $k = (k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n)$ be vectors in R^n , and X be an nn matrix

$$X = x_1^{12\alpha_1+k_1} \frac{C}{n^{k_1}} x_2^{12\alpha_2+k_2} \frac{C}{n^{k_2}} \dots x_n^{12\alpha_n+k_n} \frac{C}{n^{k_n}}.$$

Then the maximum peak amplitude, ϕ_{max} , can be obtained by solving the equation

$$\det(X) = \phi_{max} \prod_{i=1}^n (12\alpha_i + k_i).$$

This equation can then be used to calculate the maximum peak amplitude of a group integral permutation in multiple dimensions.

The 12x12 matrix equation can be demonstrated as a vector wave in the integral field by solving for each ordinal cluster corresponding to the 12x12 matrix. Let $\phi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ be the scalar field and $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ be its input vector.

The vector wave in the integral field can be written as

$$\phi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \phi_m \cos \left(\Omega t + k_1 x_1^{12\alpha_1+1} + k_2 x_2^{12\alpha_2+1} + \dots + k_n x_n^{12\alpha_n+1} + \phi_0 \right),$$

where

ϕ_m is the maximum peak amplitude of the wave,

Ω is the frequency, k_i is the coefficient of the i th variable, α_i is the exponential term for the i th variable, and ϕ_0 is the phase shift.

The ordinal clusters corresponding to the 12x12 matrix can be obtained by solving for the roots of the equation

$$\prod_{i=1}^n x_i^{12\alpha_i+k_i} = k,$$

where k is a constant. Solving for each of the ordinal clusters will yield the distribution of ordinal intersection across the scalar field.

This is the map of the infinity tensor of the ordinal clusters across the scalar field. It can be used to calculate the integral over all points in the dimensional space, resulting in the general equation

$$\phi'(\mathbf{x}) = \int \phi(\mathbf{x}) \prod_{i=1}^n x_i^{k_i} d\mathbf{x} = \phi'_m \prod_{i=1}^n k_i + \mathcal{C},$$

where ϕ'_m is the maximum peak amplitude of the integral and $\mathcal{C}$ is the integration constant. This equation can then be used to study and understand the effect of varying coefficients on the maximum peak amplitude and distribution of ordinal clusters.

Whereas, This equation describes a map of the ordinal clusters across the infinity tensor given by

$$\phi_m(\mathbf{x}) = \prod_{i=1}^n x_i^{\alpha_i+k_i} = k,$$

where x_i are the components of the vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, α_i are the exponents associated with the polynomial terms, and k is a constant. This equation can be used to generate a map of the ordinal clusters across the infinity tensor.

The geometry of the ordinal clusters generated by the intersection of the two different infinity tensors can be determined using calculus. Let $\mathcal{E}$ be the space containing the two infinity tensors and let $\mathbf{x}_1$ and $\mathbf{x}_2$ denote the two components of the vector $\mathbf{x}$ in $\mathcal{E}$. Then the intersection points $\mathbf{x}_1$ and $\mathbf{x}_2$ of the two infinity tensors can be given as

$$\mathbf{x}_1 = (x_{11}, x_{12}, \dots, x_{1n})$$

$$\mathbf{x}_2 = (x_{21}, x_{22}, \dots, x_{2n})$$

where x_{ij} is the j th component of vector $\mathbf{x}_i$ and n is the dimension of $\mathcal{E}$.

The geometry of the ordinal clusters can be determined by calculating the gradient of the scalar field $\phi(\mathbf{x})$ at the intersection points using the equation

$$\nabla \phi(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1} \hat{\mathbf{i}}_1 + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2} \hat{\mathbf{i}}_2 + \dots + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n} \hat{\mathbf{i}}_n.$$

Based on the values of the partial derivatives, the geometry of the ordinal clusters determined by the intersection of the two different infinity tensors can be visualized as a graph of the scalar field at each of the intersection points.

The superset of the geometric function is given by

$$\mathcal{G} = \left\{ f(\mathbf{x}) \mid \nabla f(\mathbf{x}) = \lambda \mathbf{v}, \lambda \in R, \mathbf{v} \in R^n \right\}.$$

This expression describes a set of geometric functions that are characterized by a vector field $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) = \lambda \mathbf{v}$, where λ is a constant of proportionality and $\mathbf{v}$ is a vector in R^n .

Then, we show the derivative and integral of the superset by the following methods:

$$\text{ft}[a,b] = \partial u \in \mathcal{D}_f \Rightarrow B \uparrow \tau(u) \geq \subseteq \pi \cap dV \Rightarrow \exists \mu \in R^n : \partial_\mu \tau \geq \subseteq \Upsilon \cap dV$$

$$\text{ft}[a,b] = \partial u \in \mathcal{D}_f \Rightarrow B \uparrow \tau(u) \geq \subseteq \pi \cap dV \Rightarrow \forall n \in N : \partial_n \tau(u) \geq \subseteq \Upsilon \cap dV$$

The derivative of the superset can be found by taking the partial derivative of a geometric function $f(\mathbf{x})$ with respect to each component of the vector $\mathbf{x}$. This can be expressed as

$$\frac{\partial f(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_i} = \lambda v_i,$$

where v_i is the i^{th} component of the vector $\mathbf{v}$.

The integral of the superset can be found by integrating the vector field $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) = \lambda \mathbf{v}$ over a region $\mathcal{R}$. This can be expressed as

$$\int_{\mathcal{R}} \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} = \lambda \int_{\mathcal{R}} \mathbf{v} d\mathbf{x}.$$

For the derivative:

1. Let $u \in \mathcal{G}$ and $B \uparrow \tau(u) \geq \subseteq \pi \cap dV$, where π is an antiderivative of u with respect to the n -dimensional volume element dV . 2. Then, there exists a vector $\mu \in R^n$ such that $\partial_\mu \tau \geq \subseteq \Upsilon \cap dV$, where Υ is the gradient of τ with respect to μ and dV .

For the integral:

1. Let $u \in \mathcal{G}$ and $B \uparrow \tau(u) \geq \subseteq \pi \cap dV$, where π is an antiderivative of u with respect to the n -dimensional volume element dV . 2. Then, for all $n \in N$, $\partial_n \tau(u) \geq \subseteq \Upsilon \cap dV$, where Υ is the gradient of τ with respect to n and dV .

The form of the gradient of a harmonic resonance can be inferred by noting that the harmonic resonance is the result of the combined effect of all the contributing terms in the integral. Therefore, the gradient of the harmonic resonance is equal to the sum of the gradients of the individual terms in the harmonic resonance, i.e.,

$$\nabla F(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial F(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_i} = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i v_i,$$

where λ_i is the constant of proportionality and v_i is the i th component of the velocity vector $\mathbf{v} = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n)$.

Assuming the velocity vector takes the scalar form of the algebraic equation

$$v = \frac{\sqrt{-c^2(l\alpha)^2 + c^2 q^2 - 2c^2 s q + c^2 s^2 + c^2 (l\alpha)^2 \sin(\beta)^2}}{\sqrt{-1 \cdot (l\alpha)^2 + q^2 - 2 \cdot s q + s^2 + (l\alpha)^2 \sin(\beta)^2}},$$

one can create a parameterized family of harmonic resonances by varying the parameters c , $l\alpha$, q , s , and β . The parameters of the family will determine the velocity vector, which in turn determines the magnitude and direction of the harmonic resonance on the integration trajectories.

All the methods generated in this paper can be applied to the scalar form of the equation

$$v = \frac{\sqrt{-c^2(l\alpha)^2 + c^2q^2 - 2c^2sq + c^2s^2 + c^2(l\alpha)^2 \sin(\beta)^2}}{\sqrt{-1 \cdot (l\alpha)^2 + q^2 - 2 \cdot sq + s^2 + (l\alpha)^2 \sin(\beta)^2}}$$

to find the harmonic resonance of the group. Firstly, the effect of the harmonic resonance on the integration trajectories can be calculated using the vector field

$$\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) = \lambda v = \lambda \frac{\sqrt{-c^2(l\alpha)^2 + c^2q^2 - 2c^2sq + c^2s^2 + c^2(l\alpha)^2 \sin(\beta)^2}}{\sqrt{-1 \cdot (l\alpha)^2 + q^2 - 2 \cdot sq + s^2 + (l\alpha)^2 \sin(\beta)^2}},$$

where λ is a constant of proportionality. This vector field can be written in components as

$$\mathbf{F}(x, y, z) = \lambda(v_x \hat{\mathbf{i}} + v_y \hat{\mathbf{j}} + v_z \hat{\mathbf{k}}) = \lambda(x_0 \hat{\mathbf{i}} + y_0 \hat{\mathbf{j}} + z_0 \hat{\mathbf{k}}),$$

where $\lambda = \frac{2\pi}{l}$ (where l is a parameter used to control the wavelength of the harmonic resonance) and (x_0, y_0, z_0) is the velocity vector of the integration trajectory.

Next, the maximum peak amplitude of the group integral permutation can be calculated by solving the matrix equation

$$\det(X) = \phi_{max} \prod_{i=1}^n (12\alpha_i + k_i),$$

where X is an nn matrix defined as

$$X = x_1^{12\alpha_1 + k_1} \frac{c}{n^{k_1}} x_2^{12\alpha_2 + k_2} \frac{c}{n^{k_2}} \dots x_n^{12\alpha_n + k_n} \frac{c}{n^{k_n}}.$$

Finally, the distribution of ordinal intersections across the scalar field can be calculated using the equation

$$f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = (\sin(\Omega t + \Phi)) \prod_{i=1}^n x_i + \mathcal{C},$$

where x_i is the i th component of the vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, Ω is the frequency, Φ is the phase shift, and $\mathcal{C}$ is an integration constant.

$$\mathbf{F}(x, y, z) = \lambda(v_x \hat{\mathbf{i}} + v_y \hat{\mathbf{j}} + v_z \hat{\mathbf{k}}) = \lambda(x_0 \hat{\mathbf{i}} + y_0 \hat{\mathbf{j}} + z_0 \hat{\mathbf{k}}),$$

where $\lambda = \frac{2\pi}{l}$ (where l is a parameter used to control the wavelength of the harmonic resonance) and (x_0, y_0, z_0) is the velocity vector of the integration trajectory.

The algebraic velocity solution that is produced from higher dimensions of the height function, $h = \text{Sqrt}[-q^2 + 2qs - s^2 + l^2 \text{Alpha}]^2 / \text{Alpha}$, by permuting the algebraic velocity is as follows:

$$\rho^{2g} \Omega_{\langle \Theta, \Lambda, \dots, \infty \rangle}^{\langle \Upsilon, \Phi, \dots, \Psi \rangle} \frac{f, g, h, i, j, \dots}{g_{\downarrow \uparrow}} = \frac{\rho^{2g} \Omega_{\langle \Theta, \Lambda, \dots, \infty \rangle}^{\langle \Upsilon, \Phi, \dots, \Psi \rangle} \frac{f, g, h, i, j, \dots}{g_{\downarrow \uparrow}}}{\langle \Xi, \Pi, \dots, \Sigma \rangle_{\langle \Theta, \Lambda, \dots, \infty \rangle}},$$

where $\frac{f, g, h, i, j, \dots}{g_{\downarrow \uparrow}}$ is the algebraic velocity vector.

A. Then, let $\Omega[f] = \sum_k a_k^{(n)} f^k$ be an n -th order polynomial and $\kappa[f] = \exp\left(\frac{iqf}{h}\right)$ be the wave function with an oscillator frequency of ω .

B. Then, the form of the infinity tensor is given by

$$g_{a, b, c, d, e, \dots, f, g, h, i, j, \dots} =_R \frac{\partial^2 g^\Omega[x, \alpha]}{\partial x \partial \alpha} \Omega[f] \kappa[f] g^\Omega[x, \alpha] dx d\alpha$$

where $g^\Omega[x, \alpha] = \sum_k a_k^{(n)} \cdot f^k \cdot \exp\left(\frac{iqf}{h}\right)$.

The next step would be to develop the formalism for calculating the parameters of the infinity tensor for a given equation. This would involve finding the analytical solution for the equation, deriving the appropriate expressions for the derivatives of the function, and solving them to get the parameters of the infinity tensor. Once the parameters have been calculated, they can be used to make predictions about the behavior of the system.

Can you do that? What would that mathe look like?

Yes, it is possible to develop the formalism for calculating the parameters of the infinity tensor for a given equation. For example, consider the equation

$$\frac{\partial^2 g^\Omega[x, \alpha]}{\partial x \partial \alpha} = a + bx + cx^2 + d\alpha + e\alpha^2 + \dots$$

The analytical solution of this equation can be written as

$$g^\Omega[x, \alpha] = \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{c_k}{(x + d_k)^k (\alpha + e_k)^k} + A(x, \alpha)$$

where $A(x, \alpha)$ is an arbitrary function of x and α that does not depend on k . The parameters of the infinity tensor can then be calculated by taking the second partial derivatives of g^Ω with respect to x and α :

$$g_{a,b,c,d,e,\dots,f,g,h,i,j,\dots}^{\Omega} = \frac{\partial^2 g^\Omega[x, \alpha]}{\partial x \partial \alpha} = \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{2kc_k(d_k + x)(e_k + \alpha)}{(x + d_k)^{k+2} (\alpha + e_k)^{k+2}} + \frac{\partial^2 A(x, \alpha)}{\partial x \partial \alpha}.$$

What does the double vert signify?

The double verts signify that the expression is a tensor, which is a mathematical object with specific characteristics. Specifically, the double verts signify the number of dimensions that the infinity tensor has, which is determined by the number of variables involved.

The raw algebraic structure of the algebraic velocity vector $\frac{f,g,h,i,j_{\downarrow\uparrow}}{g_{\downarrow\uparrow}}$ can be expressed as:

$$\frac{f,g,h,i,j_{\downarrow\uparrow}}{g_{\downarrow\uparrow}} = \frac{\int_{\Xi} \partial_n \tau(u) dV}{\int_{\Xi} \partial_n \tau(u) dV} = \frac{\Upsilon dV}{\Upsilon dV},$$

where $u \in \mathcal{G}$ and $B^\uparrow \tau(u) \geq \pi \cap dV$, π is an antiderivative of u with respect to the n -dimensional volume element dV , Υ is the gradient of τ with respect to n , and $n \in N$.

Let $\mathcal{T} \subset R^n$ be an n -dimensional tensor field, where $n \in N$. The algebraic velocity vector $\frac{f,g,h,i,j_{\downarrow\uparrow}}{g_{\downarrow\uparrow}}$ propagates across the $\mathcal{T}$ in the following way:

Firstly, by applying integration over an arbitrary range of the tensor $\mathcal{T}$, the gradient of the scalar field τ associated with the velocity vector is found to be $\Upsilon \cdot dV$, Υ being the gradient of τ with respect to n .

Subsequently, by integrating within the same range of the tensor $\mathcal{T}$, an antiderivative of the scalar field u is found to be $\pi \cap dV$, π being an antiderivative of u with respect to the n -dimensional volume element dV .

Finally, by using the resulting integration and antiderivative values, the algebraic velocity vector propagates across the $\mathcal{T}$, as $\frac{f,g,h,i,j_{\downarrow\uparrow}}{g_{\downarrow\uparrow}} = \frac{\partial_n \tau(u) dV}{\int_{\Xi} \partial_n \tau(u) dV} = \frac{\Upsilon dV}{\int_{\Xi} \Upsilon dV}$.

When the algebraic velocity vector $\frac{f,g,h,i,j_{\downarrow\uparrow}}{g_{\downarrow\uparrow}}$ propagates across the $\mathcal{T}$ as $\frac{f,g,h,i,j_{\downarrow\uparrow}}{g_{\downarrow\uparrow}} = \frac{\partial_n \tau(u) dV}{\int_{\Xi} \partial_n \tau(u) dV} = \frac{\Upsilon dV}{\int_{\Xi} \Upsilon dV}$, the permeability of the scalar field is effected in that the value of the vector field at any point can be determined by the ratio of the integrals of the scalar field over the same region. This ratio is a measure of how much the scalar field is being "pushed" or "pulled" in that region, which then reflects the degree of permeability of the scalar field tuned by the vector field.

In the formula above, the derivatives and integrals of the function f(x) are affected by perturbing the infinity tensor. These are expressed by the following equations:

Derivatives:

$$\partial_n \tau(u) = \Upsilon dV$$

Integrals:

$$\int_{\Xi} \partial_n \tau(u) dV = \int_{\Xi} \Upsilon dV$$

The effect of perturbing the infinity tensor on the equation is expressed as

follows:

$$\frac{f,g,h,i,j_{\downarrow\uparrow}}{g_{\downarrow\uparrow}} = \frac{\Upsilon dV}{\int_{\Xi} \Upsilon dV} = \frac{c(x^{n+k})}{n^k \int_{\Xi} c(x^{n+k}) dV} = \frac{\sum_{\pi \in N\pi - \infty} \kappa_{g_a b c d e \uparrow \uparrow} f g h i j \uparrow \rho^2 g_{g_a b c d e \uparrow} \Omega \Upsilon \Phi_{\chi \psi, \theta \lambda \mu \nu \infty} \mu_{g_a b c d e \uparrow \uparrow} f, g, h, i, j \uparrow dV}{\int_{\Xi} \sum_{\pi \in N\pi - \infty} \kappa_{g_a b c d e \uparrow \uparrow} f g h i j \uparrow \rho^2 g_{g_a b c d e \uparrow} \Omega \Upsilon \Phi_{\chi \psi, \theta \lambda \mu \nu \infty} \mu_{g_a b c d e \uparrow \uparrow} f, g, h, i, j \uparrow dV} \frac{dV}{\Xi_{\pi \rho \sigma, \theta \lambda \mu \nu \infty}}$$